

Theoretical insight of OH-initiated mechanistic pathways and kinetics of n-butyl nitrate ($\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{ONO}_2$) at 298 K and 1 atm[†]

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Manuscript received 06 December 2017, accepted 20 December 2017

Abstract : A detailed density functional studies of the reaction of n-butyl nitrate initiated by OH radical as well as atmospheric life-time of the titled molecule have been carried out by using hybrid functional M06-2X method along with 6-311+G(d,p) basis set. We obtain the possible H-abstraction channels of the reaction of n-butyl nitrate with OH radical on the potential energy surface along with the thermochemistry associated with it. The overall rate constant as well as individual rate constants for four plausible pathways of the reaction are calculated using the canonical transition state theory (CTST) at 298 K and 1 atm. Kinetically, the path which involves the abstraction of H atom from the -OCH₂ site of $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{ONO}_2$ is found to be the dominant one and the calculated overall rate constant is $3.63 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which is in good agreement with the experimentally value, $1.66 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The reported kinetic and thermo-chemical results in this work would be helpful for further degradation and decomposition pathways of the generated radical into the atmosphere.

Keywords : n-Butyl nitrate, VOCs, OH radicals, M06-2X functional, rate constant, atmospheric lifetime.

Introduction

Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) are organic substances which have a low boiling point at room temperature. Due to their high vapour pressure and low boiling point, they easily vaporize into the atmosphere from industrial materials like paints, adhesives, chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) etc. Considerable emissions of VOCs into the troposphere are a worldwide problem caused from anthropogenic as well as biogenic sources¹. Organic nitrates are formed as intermediates during the atmospheric oxidation of VOCs and oxygenated VOCs in the presence of nitrogen oxides². Tropospheric ozone is formed by the OH oxidation of VOCs in the presence of NO. Organic nitrates are also formed through this process³.

Organic nitrates have the long tropospheric lifetime, which makes them a storehouse of NO_x in the troposphere. NO_x is a key catalyst for ozone formation and destruction^{4,5}. These nitrates are likely to impact a long range distribution of NO_x and ozone in the troposphere, highly influencing the extent of Global Warming. In the troposphere, VOCs are transformed by the chemical processes of photolysis (at wavelengths > 290 nm), reaction with the OH radical (typically during daylight hours), reaction with the NO₃ radical during night-time hours, reaction with O₃, and in coastal and marine areas reaction with Cl atoms during daylight hours^{6,7}. Hence, it is necessary to probe into the degradation of these organic nitrates to determine their impact on the atmo-

[†]Professor A. S. R. Anjaneyulu 60th Birthday Commemoration Lecture (2016).

sphere. The experimental studies on the kinetics of the reaction of the OH radical with n-butyl nitrate have already been performed by Bedjanian *et al.*¹ using a low-pressure flow tube reactor combined with a quadrupole mass spectrometer (QMS). The rate constant of the reaction was determined under pseudo-first order conditions from the kinetics of OH consumption in high excess of the nitrates¹. The overall rate constant was measured as a function of temperature, $k = 1.0 \times 10^{-13} (T/298)^{3.36} \exp(838/T)$ ($T = 288-500$ K) $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$. The available data on the rate constant of the reaction was initially limited to a few studies at room temperature⁸⁻¹¹. Although, the experimental investigations give the overall rate constant and the tropospheric lifetime of the nitrate with OH radical, it fails to indicate the detail thermochemistry and the possible reaction channels. In the present work, we have considered n-butyl nitrate ($\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{ONO}_2$) and performed computational studies on four reaction channels involved in the reaction with OH radical. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first computational study on the titled reaction.

There are four possible ways of H-abstraction from $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{ONO}_2$ by OH radical. The removal of H may occur from either one of the four sites which lead to four reaction channels :

This computational work is focused on the contribution of all the reaction channels to the overall rate constant. We have studied the kinetics and thermochemistry associated with each of the pathways using DFT method. Initially, geometry optimization and frequency calculation were performed at hybrid density functional M06-2X method¹² along with 6-311+G(d,p) basis set. The rate constants for the four pathways were calculated using the canonical

transition state theory (CTST) and the thermo-chemical properties associated with each of the channels were also determined at 298 K and 1 atm. The main objective is to determine the contribution of all the four channels to the overall rate constant, deduce the predominant pathway for the reaction and compare the result with the experimental rate constant¹.

Computational details

Geometry optimization was carried out using hybrid density functional M06-2X method along with 6-311+G(d,p) basis set. The reactants ($\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{ONO}_2$ and OH radical), products (P1, P2, P3, P4 and H_2O) along with the various transition states (TS1 to TS4), reactant complexes (RCs) and product complexes (PCs) were created using Gaussian View. Experimental studies done in the past have revealed that the M06-2X hybrid density functional method gives good results for determining the kinetics and thermochemistry involved¹³⁻¹⁷. Apart from optimization, the frequency calculation was also performed for all the species at the same level of theory. The frequency calculation provides a check on the nature of the stationary points on the potential energy surface (PES)¹⁸. The transition states were characterized by only one imaginary frequency. All other stationary points, except the TS, have been characterized by real positive vibrational frequencies. In addition to characterizing the stationary points, the frequency calculation also provides the zero point energy (ZPE)¹⁸. ZPE is the energy of the molecule at absolute zero. For accuracy, the ZPE value must be added to the total energy of the species. Intrinsic Reaction Coordinate (IRC) calculations¹⁹ were performed to obtain the minimum energy pathway connecting the reactants and the products via the transition state. IRC calculation gives an animated view of the reaction path. The initial geometry considered was that of the transition state and the reaction path was followed in both the directions. All the calculations have been performed by using Gaussian 09 suite of the program²⁰.

The rate constants for the four H-abstraction routes have been calculated using the canonical transition state theory (CTST)²¹⁻²³ which includes a tunnelling correction factor.

$$k = \sigma_r \Gamma(T) \frac{k_B T}{h} \frac{Q_{TS}^\ddagger}{Q_R} \exp \frac{-\Delta E^\ddagger}{RT} \quad (1)$$

In this equation, σ_r allows for the number of equivalent reaction paths, for example, $\sigma_r = 4$ for $H \rightarrow CH_4$, Q stands for the partition function for the specified species and ΔE^\ddagger is the difference in energy between the zeroth levels in the transition state and in the reactants²⁴, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, h is the Planck's constant and R represents the universal gas constant. The inclusion of a tunnelling factor, $\Gamma(T)$ is especially important in those bimolecular reactions where an H-atom is transferred, e.g. $OH + CH_4 \rightarrow H_2O + CH_3$. Reactions of this type are important in the Earth's atmosphere and in combustion systems²⁴. The tunnelling correction was estimated by using Eckart's unsymmetrical barrier method^{25,26}.

Barrier height for a particular reaction channel was determined from the energy (including ZPE) difference between TS and reactants. Since OH-initiated having negative energy barrier reaction follows indirect mechanism, so the reaction of $CH_3CH_2CH_2CH_2ONO_2$ by OH radicals also proceeds via two step mechanism. The first step involves a fast pre-equilibrium (K_{eq}) between the reactants and the hydrogen bonded reaction complex and the second step is the hydrogen abstraction with the rate constant k_2 . The equilibrium constant (K_{eq}) and the rate constant (k_2) can be given by the following expression as

$$K_{eq} = \frac{Q_{RC}}{Q_R} \exp (E_R - E_{RC})/RT \quad (2)$$

$$k_2 = \sigma_r \Gamma(T) \frac{k_B T}{h} \frac{Q_{TS}^\ddagger}{Q_{RC}} \exp (E_{RC} - E_{TS})/RT \quad (3)$$

Thus, the rate constant for reaction channels (R1-R5) involving the pre-reaction complex is then ob-

tained by product K_{eq} and k_2 and given as,

$$k = K_{eq} \times k_2 = \sigma_r \Gamma(T) \frac{k_B T}{h} \frac{Q_{TS}^\ddagger}{Q_R} \exp (E_{TS} - E_R)/RT \quad (4)$$

where Q_R , Q_{RC} and Q_{TS} represents the total partition functions (per unit volume) of the reactants, reaction complex and the transition state respectively and E_{TS} , E_{RC} and E_R are their corresponding ZPE corrected total energies. Thus, the eq. (4) is similar as eq. (1) that obtained during usual CTST used for the determination of rate constant and barrier height of a direct reaction, irrespective of the energy of pre-reactive hydrogen bonded complexes. However, the value of $\Gamma(T)$ will evidently be different due to pre-reaction complex formation and as a result will affect the total rate constant.

The total partition functions for the species were obtained at 298 K from the frequency calculations performed at M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level. The total partition function for a particular species is a product of its translational, rotational, vibrational and electronic partition functions²⁷ i.e. $Q = Q_{trans} \times Q_{rot} \times Q_{vib} \times Q_{elec}$. During the calculation of total partition function for OH radical, its electronic partition function was corrected by considering the excited state of OH radical with a 140 cm^{-1} splitting by using the expression given below :

$$Q_{elec}(OH) = 2 + 2 \exp \left(\frac{-140 (\text{cm}^{-1}) hc_0}{kT} \right) \quad (5)$$

where h is the Planck's constant, c_0 is the speed of light in cm/s and k is the Boltzmann's constant. The OH partition functions were corrected at 298 K using the above expression.

The C-H bond dissociation energies (BDE) for the four H-abstraction channels were calculated by taking into account the removal of an H-atom from the alkyl nitrate (e.g. $R \rightarrow P1 + H$).

Thus, BDEs of C-H bonds involved during reactions (R1-R4) were calculated in terms of eq. (6) :

$$BD E_0(A-B) = E_0(A^\bullet) + E_0(A^\bullet) - E_0(A-B) \quad (6)$$

where E_0 's are the zero-point corrected total energy of the corresponding species. A^\bullet and B^\bullet are the radical species formed as a result of homolytic fission of the covalent bond. From the analysis of BDE, we can perform a comparative study on the ease of H-removal from the four different sites. It gives us a brief idea about the C-H bond strength at the positions.

Results and discussion

The results of the detailed thermochemistry calculations associated with the four reaction channels (R1-R4) are presented in Table 1. The calculations are performed at M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory. The $\Delta_r H^0$ and $\Delta_r G^0$ values for all the pathways are found to be negative. The reaction channels are therefore, exothermic ($\Delta_r H^0 < 0$) and thermodynamically feasible ($\Delta_r G^0 < 0$) in nature.

Table 1. Reaction enthalpy and Gibb's free energy data (in kcal/mol) at 298 K for the four H-abstraction channels calculated at M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory

Reaction channels	M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level	
	$\Delta_r H^0$	$\Delta_r G^0$
R + OH \rightarrow P1 + H ₂ O	-18.44	-20.24
R + OH \rightarrow P2 + H ₂ O	-18.39	-20.44
R + OH \rightarrow P3 + H ₂ O	-18.79	-20.85
R + OH \rightarrow P4 + H ₂ O	-15.70	-17.36

It is clear from Table 1 that all reaction channels are exothermic and feasible. However, the value of $\Delta_r H^0$ and $\Delta_r G^0$ are more negative for pathway 3. This implies that the product obtained from this pathway is thermodynamically more feasible than the other three reaction channels. The results of the thermochemistry calculations for the first three channels are quite close. Therefore, it does not necessarily indicate the pathway which is expected to have the fastest rate constant for the titled reaction. However, it indicates that pathway 4 is the thermodynamically least preferred channel.

The optimized geometries for all the species at M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory are shown in

Fig. 1. From the optimized CH₃CH₂CH₂CH₂ONO₂ molecule, it is clear that the H-atoms attached to the same carbon atom are equivalent in nature. The C-H bond lengths are similar at a particular position in the alkyl chain. This indicates the possibility of four H-abstraction channels at the four C-positions (-CH₂ONO₂, -CH₂CH₂CH₃, -CH₂CH₃ and -CH₃). The bond dissociation energy for the C-H bond at all the four positions is determined. The D°_{298} values (kcal mol⁻¹) for C-H bonds obtained from the M06-2X level calculations in the positions, -CH₂ONO₂, -CH₂CH₂CH₃, -CH₂CH₃ and -CH₃ amount to be 97.66, 97.72, 97.31 and 100.40, respectively. The values of BDE are listed in Table 2.

The BDE values are the lowest for pathway 3, implying that the C-H bond breaking is the easiest for this pathway and BDE is observed to be the highest for pathway 4, making it the least favoured route for H-abstraction. The D°_{298} values of the first three reaction channels are quite close.

There are four transition states for the reaction CH₃CH₂CH₂CH₂ONO₂ + OH for the four different reaction channels. The reactant complexes (RC) named as RC1, RC2, RC3, RC4 and product complexes (PC) named as the same at the entry and exit channel respectively of the TS have been validated in the present work. In the RCs, no appreciable change in the bond lengths of CH₃CH₂CH₂CH₂ONO₂ is observed with the approach of OH radical. At the TS, the C-H bond breaking and a new O-H bond formation take place simultaneously. The O-H bond which forms is longer than the equilibrium O-H distance (0.972 Å) in H₂O. The product complexes are possibly formed due to weak H-bonding between the CH₃CH₂CH₂CH₂ONO₂ and OH radical through C-H...O and O-H...O at the exit channel. Also, the presence of a -NO₃ influences the H-bonding. The C-H bond length at the site of radical formation and the O-H bond formed are adjusted and all other bond lengths get closer to those in the equilibrium position. The RCs and PCs were obtained from the minimum energy path connecting the reactants and the

products via the TS during the IRC calculation. Fig. 1 shows the optimized geometry of all the species

involved in the reaction, $\bullet\text{OH} + n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9\text{ONO}_2 \rightarrow$ products. The most remarkable changes are observed

Fig. 1. Optimized structures of all the species involved in the four reaction channels of the titled reaction at M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory.

in the optimized geometry of the transition states (TS) where the simultaneous removal of H atom from the C-H bond and the formation of a new O-H bond between the removed H and the O atom of the OH

radical can be seen. In the transition states (TS1 to TS4), the new O-H bonds being formed are longer as compared to the C-H bonds which are being broken. This implies that the reaction barriers are closer

Table 2. The bond dissociation energies (D°_{298}) of the C-H bond for the four possible pathways at M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory

Reaction channels	M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level D°_{298} (in kcal/mol)
R \rightarrow P1 + H	97.66
R \rightarrow P2 + H	97.72
R \rightarrow P3 + H	97.31
R \rightarrow P4 + H	100.40

to the reactant side in all the four pathways and the reactions will proceed via early transition state structure and the Hammond's postulate²⁸ can be applied to the exothermic reaction channels.

The frequency calculations carried out at M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) give us the vibrational frequencies of all the species in the reaction channels. The vibrational frequencies are recorded in Table 3. All

Table 3. Vibrational frequencies (298 K) of all species at M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory. The transition states are characterized by one imaginary frequency (shown as bold)

Species	Vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1})											
	60	77	112	137	158	256	271	327	452	645	751	754
R	808	827	921	960	962	1058	1078	1095	1164	1192	1261	1306
	1324	1340	1377	1406	1419	1451	1497	1502	1509	1514	1527	1783
	3052	3055	3072	3083	3087	3116	3128	3138	3144			
OH	3766											
RC1	47	48	75	87	113	141	154	173	185	261	273	329
	404	452	648	747	756	809	826	921	957	980	1056	1073
	1095	1163	1192	1260	1298	1325	1332	1377	1401	1421	1454	1495
	1499	1509	1511	1524	1766	3046	3055	3062	3080	3091	3109	3127
	3144	3154	3773									
RC2	37	46	63	86	111	117	137	180	235	269	308	331
	448	486	647	748	751	811	829	920	958	966	1055	1069
	1094	1163	1193	1260	1297	1323	1332	1379	1402	1420	1452	1496
	1500	1504	1513	1523	1779	3043	3049	3058	3079	3087	3108	3124
	3129	3151	3757									
RC3	37	55	61	102	117	120	151	166	170	226	251	280
	331	451	645	745	754	810	827	915	958	967	1055	1077
	1095	1163	1189	1260	1295	1319	1327	1375	1399	1416	1451	1494
	1499	1505	1513	1527	1779	3020	3047	3057	3066	3083	3108	3119
	3132	3149	3779									
RC4	42	60	61	85	116	145	155	157	164	279	309	310
	328	453	645	744	753	812	829	915	953	965	1055	1077
	1093	1162	1192	1261	1293	1321	1326	1376	1398	1410	1452	1492
	1501	1506	1520	1527	1779	3033	3037	3058	3066	3090	3101	3108
	3121	3146	3761									
TS1	908i	55	62	68	99	132	161	192	252	273	322	329
	440	641	685	742	754	808	847	908	922	968	1014	1061
	1100	1138	1164	1176	1248	1293	1323	1335	1373	1400	1421	1427
	1451	1488	1499	1507	1513	1792	3042	3050	3053	3083	3101	3125
	3127	3134	3772									
TS2	861i	50	53	73	103	109	153	164	249	268	308	323
	452	643	686	731	756	805	818	927	957	985	1046	1064
	1075	1119	1163	1195	1263	1298	1310	1351	1377	1396	1419	1436
	1484	1490	1506	1509	1516	1792	3040	3055	3080	3081	3099	3131
	3138	3141	3792									

Table-3 (contd.)

TS3	654i	43	53	80	98	119	141	161	192	242	273	330
	450	646	654	755	786	814	830	910	951	968	1053	1074
	1080	1155	1173	1193	1259	1294	1326	1365	1388	1398	1415	1453
	1488	1496	1499	1530	1533	1782	3045	3052	3078	3091	3107	3117
	3141	3159	3797									
TS4	815i	40	51	87	107	117	140	163	182	274	328	332
	454	646	713	754	774	815	840	896	955	969	1045	1078
	1097	1123	1174	1222	1279	1309	1312	1327	1341	1375	1396	1410
	1450	1471	1486	1507	1527	1783	3029	3060	3075	3079	3086	3111
	3139	3155	3798									
PC1	34	51	70	90	120	151	162	206	217	230	283	311
	336	389	392	465	648	708	745	784	874	883	921	1048
	1080	1105	1157	1169	1255	1283	1325	1359	1389	1416	1441	1478
	1498	1503	1509	1618	1793	2996	3044	3049	3082	3099	3122	3128
	3230	3869	3980									
PC2	33	50	59	104	119	143	192	221	238	262	308	324
	334	428	458	534	617	743	779	815	880	951	981	985
	1034	1067	1174	1182	1263	1290	1325	1375	1406	1421	1460	1476
	1503	1504	1514	1613	1780	2994	3056	3094	3104	3130	3151	3160
	3198	3861	3983									
PC3	47	55	58	97	118	135	154	164	167	189	233	268
	294	333	448	493	646	756	805	824	923	972	976	1045
	1076	1097	1148	1175	1249	1296	1325	1381	1406	1430	1458	1483
	1486	1495	1529	1588	1779	2995	3003	3072	3097	3106	3122	3175
	3177	3861	3979									
PC4	40	49	91	107	125	150	183	191	225	242	289	302
	319	335	454	569	646	755	764	815	856	909	967	1070
	1075	1083	1111	1161	1224	1297	1307	1331	1376	1410	1449	1470
	1482	1508	1526	1614	1777	3000	3055	3076	3087	3127	3152	3156
	3261	3852	3981									
P1	44	51	103	133	158	244	278	329	447	520	649	739
	755	777	880	909	935	1055	1091	1112	1158	1174	1252	1281
	1326	1356	1394	1422	1429	1482	1500	1507	1515	1802	3003	3049
	3053	3062	3099	3127	3135	3241						
P2	38	50	63	133	223	241	281	287	447	541	606	758
	772	810	870	956	984	997	1040	1071	1150	1183	1264	1279
	1325	1371	1417	1427	1446	1472	1505	1507	1509	1773	3004	3055
	3065	3079	3136	3147	3151	3203						
P3	43	68	94	116	142	167	281	326	436	449	644	754
	785	816	924	966	970	1036	1076	1091	1152	1174	1235	1292
	1311	1377	1404	1432	1453	1481	1484	1494	1522	1783	3000	3004
	3068	3075	3083	3133	3142	3187						
P4	58	76	112	130	144	161	277	328	442	481	646	745
	756	812	843	923	959	1046	1081	1100	1105	1165	1224	1294
	1312	1328	1377	1404	1451	1472	1479	1505	1526	1784	2984	3063
	3075	3084	3122	3145	3165	3275						
H ₂ O	1596	3894	4000									

the species except the transition states possess real positive vibrational frequencies signifying stable minima. The transition states (TS1 to TS4) are characterized by the existence of only one imaginary vibrational frequency (in cm^{-1}) at **908i**, **861i**, **654i**, and **815i** respectively. The imaginary frequencies validate the presence of the transition states connecting the reactants and the products in the reaction channels. IRC calculation is performed at the same level of theory to visualize the smooth pathway which connects the reactant side to the product side via the transition state. Frequency calculation also gives us the zero point energies (ZPE) of the species. The ZPE corrected total energies of the species along with the relative energy barrier are recorded in Table 4. The reaction profile diagrams of the reaction channels with the results obtained at M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory are shown in Fig. 2. The energies of the reactants are considered as zero and the energies of all other species are calculated with respect to the reactants. The barrier heights for the four pathways (1 to 4) are -0.56 , -0.23 , 0.24

Table 4. Zero-point corrected total energies (E_0) and the relative energy (R.E.) of all the species calculated at 298 K

Species	M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p)	
	E_0 (Hartree)	R.E. (kcal/mol)
R + OH	-513.6465	0
RC1	-513.6531	-4.18
RC2	-513.6544	-4.98
RC3	-513.6505	-2.54
RC4	-513.6491	-1.63
TS1	-513.6473	-0.56
TS2	-513.6468	-0.23
TS3	-513.6461	0.24
TS4	-513.6437	1.73
PC1	-513.6838	-23.47
PC2	-513.6833	-23.10
PC3	-513.6829	-22.84
PC4	-513.6774	-19.45
P1 + H ₂ O	-513.6766	-18.91
P2 + H ₂ O	-513.6765	-18.88
P3 + H ₂ O	-513.6773	-19.38
P4 + H ₂ O	-513.6723	-16.24

and $1.73 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, respectively. Pathway 1 has the least barrier height, indicating that it may be the kinetically favoured route. These results are not similar to that obtained from the thermodynamic parameters. However, it is also observed the thermodynamic properties of the first three channels are quite close.

The rate constants for the four H-abstraction channels were calculated using CTST. Using Eckart's unsymmetrical barrier, the tunnelling factor was calculated for TS1 to TS4. The tunnelling correction at 298 K for the TS1, TS2, TS3 and TS4 are found to be 2.20, 2.12, 1.50 and 1.89, respectively at the M06-2X level of theory. The partition functions (Q) determined from the computational calculations, tunnelling correction (Γ) and activation energy (ΔE^\ddagger) values were used to calculate the rate constants. The rate constants for the four pathways : $-\text{CH}_2\text{ONO}_2$, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$, $-\text{CH}_3$ pathways are 1.55×10^{-12} , 1.32×10^{-12} , 6.66×10^{-13} and $9.45 \times 10^{-14} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively, at 298 K. The overall rate constant k_{OH} for the titled reaction at M06-2X level is calculated to be $3.63 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ which is three times the experimental rate constant $1.66 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ reported by Bedjanian *et al.*¹. From the rate constant values for the four channels, it is evident that at M06-2X level, pathway 1 is found to be the kinetically dominant route for the reaction to take place and pathway 4 is both thermodynamically and kinetically least favoured route. The rate constants for the four channels follow the order : Path 4 < Path 3 < Path 2 < Path 1.

Atmospheric Implications and Global Warming Potentials (GWPs)

Assuming that the degradation of n-butyl nitrate in the atmosphere primarily occurs by the OH radical, we can calculate the atmospheric lifetime (τ_{eff}) of $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{ONO}_2$. τ_{eff} for the titled species can be expressed as²⁹ :

$$\tau_{\text{eff}} \approx \tau_{\text{OH}} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 2. Relative energy profile diagram for the $n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9\text{ONO}_2 + \bullet\text{OH}$ reaction obtained at M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory.

Table 5. Rate constants (k) for the four reaction channels determined at M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory	
$T = 298 \text{ K}$	M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level
Reaction channels	$k \text{ (cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}$
$\text{R} + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{P1} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	1.55×10^{-12}
$\text{R} + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{P2} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	1.32×10^{-12}
$\text{R} + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{P3} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.67×10^{-12}
$\text{R} + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{P4} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.09×10^{-12}
Overall rate constant	3.63×10^{-12}
(This work)	
Experimental rate constant	1.66×10^{-12}
(Bedjanian <i>et al.</i> ¹)	

where $\tau_{\text{OH}} = (k_{\text{OH}} \times [\text{OH}])^{-1}$. The global average concentration of OH radical is taken as $1 \times 10^6 \text{ mol cm}^{-3}$ this paper³⁰. The calculated value of average rate constant (k_{OH}) at M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level is $3.63 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The atmospheric lifetime is estimated to be 3.2 days (0.008 years) by using eq. (7) which is in reasonable agreement with the experimentally available atmospheric lifetime value, 7 days¹. Due to a very short lifetime, this molecule has negligible contribution to the global warming potential.

Conclusions

The energy profile diagrams and the kinetics data for the reaction $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{ONO}_2$ with OH radicals investigated at M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory have been systematically presented in this work. We have studied four plausible reaction pathways for the titled reaction. The hydrogen abstraction reactions of n-butyl nitrate with OH radicals proceed by a complex indirect mechanism involving the formation of reactant complexes at the entrance channel and product complexes at the exit channel. The kinetically dominant reaction channel is pathway 1 and the results of the thermodynamic calculations for the first three routes do not vary much. In this work, it is understood that thermodynamically and kinetically, pathway 4 is the least preferred route for the titled reaction. The barrier height for dominant pathway 1 calculated at the M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p) level is found to be minimum and the rate constant for the same pathway of H atom abstraction is found to be $1.55 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Also, the overall rate constant at 298 K and 1 atm is calculated to be $3.63 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The increasing order for the rate constants of the reaction channels is : Path 4 < Path 3 < Path 2 < Path 1. The atmospheric lifetime of $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{ONO}_2$ is found to be 3.2 days which indicate that it will have no significant effect on ozone and very low impact on climate change. These data can be useful for further thermo kinetic modelling of other atmospheric reactions involving these species.

Acknowledgements

Susmita Baruah is thankful to IASc-INSA-NASI for providing the Summer Research Fellowship 2017 (Application No. CHES828). NKG is also thankful to University Grants Commission (UGC), New Delhi for providing Dr. D. S. Kothari Post-Doctoral Fellowship (Award Letter No : F.4-2/2006(BSR)/CH/14-15/0217).

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